

Cooperative Teaching Approach as a Means to Improve the Understanding of Form Two Science Students in the Concept of the Human Digestive System

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Abstract

The study was to improve students' understanding in human digestive system using Cooperative Teaching Approach in Siddiq Senior High School in Agona Nyarkrom in the Central Region of the Republic of Ghana. The major research design adopted for this research was Action Research Design which made use of a Case Study at Siddiq Senior High School. The accessible population of the study was made up of all the 35 second year students of the Science class who make up 5.83% of the school's population. Out of the 35 students, 25 representing 71.43% of the class were boys whilst the remaining 10 representing 28.57% were girls. The sampling technique used was purposive sampling. Class Test was the main instrument for the data collection. The results of the pre-test showed that majority of the target group did not do well; none of them was able to score marks ranging from five to ten in both identifying the parts and relating the parts to their functions of the human digestive system. This implies that the students had difficulty in human digestive system which needed attention. However, the post-test showed that majority of the students of the accessible group passed with marks ranging between ten and twenty inclusive. This indicated that the use of cooperative teaching approach was effective in improving their understanding of the concept. Based on the findings, the researcher recommends that biology teachers should involve students in cooperative small group instruction to help students learn better.

Keywords: Cooperative teaching approach, Science, Human digestive system, Understanding.

Introduction

Science is undoubtedly the bedrock of every nation; this means for any nation to fully achieve its developmental goals, there is the need to give utmost attention to science education and Ghana is of no exception, if she is to meet this era of rapid global scientific and technological advancement. In the light of this, government has adopted conscious efforts and pragmatic measures over the years to improve the teaching and learning of science across the various educational ladders in Ghana.

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267

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In Ghana, Science education concentrates on the teaching of science concepts, methods of teaching and addressing misconceptions held by learners regarding science concepts. Science as a discipline is taught in the basic schools (primary and junior high schools), senior high schools and tertiary. Science as a discipline has branches such as biology, physics, chemistry, medicine, agriculture and many others. These branches are mostly termed as subjects in the various schools. Each branch of science consists of a body of knowledge which is broken into topics which are organized in a related manner such that the understanding of one topic aids the understanding of the next. The teaching and learning of science in schools has become an unbendable tool world-wide to the immense contribution to science and technology in providing massive solutions to some of the challenges that confront man. Therefore, the study of science is imperative for the socio-economic development of every nation.

Science as a discipline consists of different concepts with varying levels of complexities and therefore there is the need to adopt different and suitable teaching strategies to map each concept in order to aid the understanding of the students. Generally, students have challenges in learning science due to several factors; inability to comprehend what is being taught due to teachers' ineffective teaching methods and assessment strategies. The acquisition of knowledge in assessment is essential for instructors to improve their teaching practices in the classroom, thereby enhancing students' learning outcomes (Konadu, 2025). Students' mental health state can further influence their learning abilities. Anxiety and depression are prevalent mental health issues encountered by students across all educational levels. According to Konadu, Aduse-Poku and Zaagbli (2025), these concerns affect the rate at which students comprehend, engage, and achieve the necessary scores on assessments. Classroom engagement is a critical factor in academic success, as it is directly influenced by the emotional states of students (Konadu, Aduse-Poku, & Zaagbli, 2025). This can be achieved by instructing students in social and emotional competencies. The implementation of social and emotional learning (SEL) has been linked to a reduction in classroom disruptions and an improvement in the quality of teacher-student relationships, thereby fostering a more collaborative and harmonious educational environment (Konadu, 2025). Also, the social and emotional wellbeing of teachers further determines students' SEL, consequently, identifying solutions to address the needs of teachers in this regard will have a positive impact on their students, thereby improving their learning outcomes, as per Konadu (2025).

Teaching a concept like the human digestive system would be well understood by the students if Cooperative Teaching Approach is used with the aid of well-prepared Teaching and learning materials. Cooperative learning is the educational learning situation where learning occurs while two or more students are together to complete a common task (Siegel, 2005). Cooperative learning also involves students working together to achieve common goals or complete group tasks – goals and tasks that they would be unable to complete by themselves learning together and learning alone method (Johnson & Johnson, 1994). The Researcher after conducting a class test to assess the level of students understanding of the subject matter and measure students'

performance has unveiled their impoverished knowledge in the concept of human digestive system. The marks obtained by the students in the class test were nothing to write about. Further investigations through questions on their knowledge of the subject matter were found to be insignificant. It is as a result of the aforementioned that the researcher saw it a necessity to investigate the effect of using teaching and learning materials on senior high school students performance in studying the concept of human digestive system in Biology in S.H.S 2 Science students at Siddiq Senior High School at Agona Nyarkrom in the Agona West District of the Central Region of the Republic of Ghana. Therefore, it is because of this background that the Researcher chose this study to find out the effect of such influence.

Problem statement

A class test was conducted to find out the magnitude of the perceived problem. The class test consisted of two parts. The first part was to assess the level of the students' knowledge in determining the parts of the human digestive system while the second part was to assess their level of knowledge in relating the parts of the digestive to their functions. Again, there were ten questions in each part. In all, there were twenty questions for the class test. Ten marks were allocated for each part, meaning the total marks allocated for the test were twenty. The number of students present at the time of the test was thirty-five. The scripts were marked subsequently, and the following discoveries were made: For part one, twenty-five students representing 71.429% of the students who took the test scored below the pass mark of five whilst ten students representing 28.571% of the students who took the test scored from the pass mark five and above. For part two, twenty-eight students representing 80% of the students who took the test scored below the pass mark of five whilst seven of the students representing 20% of the students who took the test scored from the pass mark five and above. The results of the class test confirmed the intensity of the perceived problem in the class and hence there is the need for a way forward to tackle the problem.

From the class test conducted and the interactions the researcher had with the students, the poor knowledge of the students on the concept of the human digestive system may be attributed to the following factors: firstly, the concept of the human digestive system is mostly taught in abstract form and therefore, they find it difficult to retain what is learnt. Secondly, most of them admitted having no knowledge in identifying the associated organs and glands of the human digestive system. Finally, they lack sufficient knowledge in relating the parts of the human digestive system to their functions. Based on the diagnosis stated, it is undisputable fact that students in SHS two science class have poor knowledge in the concept of human digestive system which needed to be given all the necessary attention it deserved. Majority of the students could not appropriately determine the parts of the human digestive system. Again, most of them could not relate the parts of the human digestive system to their functions. The Researcher discovered this when he was teaching the parts of the human digestive system and their functions to form two

science class and hence there is the need to adopt measures to improve their understanding on the concept of digestive system.

Purpose of the study

The purpose of this study was to use Cooperative Teaching Approach to enhance the understanding of students in the concept, human digestive system among form two science students of Siddiq Senior High school, Agona Nyarkrom. The study therefore finds answer to the question: What is the impact of Cooperative Teaching Approach on the academic achievement of students in the concept, the human digestive system?

Theoretical foundation of the study

Cooperative learning is fundamentally a constructivist learning strategy. It is “child centered ” learning; child centered learning is a learning strategy that actively involves the student in the teaching and learning process. In this learning strategy, students are guided to discover the inter relationship or the subject structure by themselves through proper guided activities (Ross and Smyth, 1995). Piaget (1950) found that students working in cooperative groups would participate in discussions. As a natural part of these discussions, conflicts would occur, and solutions were achieved. According to Johnson and Johnson (2005), conflict helped group members to pause and consider others’ views. When group members were presented with opposing views, it caused cognitive restructuring. This resulted in improved academic performance of group members (Johnson et al., 1998). Vygotsky (1978) concluded that it was social. His theory is based on students working together to solve, learn and understand problems.

Conceptual framework

Cooperative learning is a small group of students working together to increase their personal learning and that of their group members. Students are placed into small groups, and the teacher gives directions and assignments. The group works until all the members of the group understand and complete the task (Johnson and Johnson, 2005). Cooperative learning is the educational learning situation where learning occurs while two or more students are together to complete a common task (Siegel, 2005). Cooperative learning also involves students working together to achieve common goals or complete group tasks – goals and tasks that they would be unable to complete by themselves learning together and learning alone method (Johnson & Johnson, 1994). Interest in cooperative learning gathered momentum in the early 1980s with the publication of the first meta-analysis involving 122 studies on the effects of cooperative, competitive, and individualistic goal structures on students’ achievement and productivity in a sample of North American schools (Johnson, Maruyama, Johnson, Nelson, & Skon, 1981). The results showed that cooperation was more effective than interpersonal competition and individualistic efforts; cooperation with intergroup competition was also superior to interpersonal competition and individualistic efforts; and there were no significant differences between

interpersonal competitive and individualistic efforts. There is many cooperative learning which has been identified, and these include: the jigsaw, learning together, student team-achievement divisions.

Jigsaw: The Jigsaw method was developed by Elliot Aronson in 1978. In the Jigsaw method, students are assigned to multi-member teams to work on academic material that has been divided into sections. Each member of the group is assigned a section of study in which he or she becomes an expert. Experts are then assigned to expert groups in which the members of the group discuss the information and decide on the best way to present the material to members of their home teams. After the students have mastered the material, group members return to their home teams to teach the other members the material.

Learning together: Learning together is a cooperative learning strategy created by David W. Johnson and Roger T. Johnson. Learning together was originally designed to help train teachers how to use cooperative learning groups in the classroom at the University of Minnesota in 1966. In the learning together strategy, cooperative effort includes five basic elements: face-to-face interaction, social skills, group processing, positive interdependence, and individual accountability (Johnson & Johnson, 1989). Human interaction is essential for human survival. The definition of social interdependence in education can be summarized as “students’ efforts to achieve and develop positive relationships, adjust psychologically, and show social competence” (Johnson et al., 1998).

Student teams-achievement divisions: Student Teams-Achievement Divisions is a cooperative learning strategy created by Robert Slavin in which groups of four work within their teams to master a lesson presented by the teacher. Students take individualized quizzes, which are compared to past performances, and then team scores are put together based on the extent to which the students in the group meet or surpass past performance (Slavin, 1995). Teams that meet the appropriate criteria may earn some kind of reward from the teacher.

Methodology

The study was carried out at Siddiq Senior High School, Form Two Science class in Agona Nyarkrom in the Central Region of the Republic of Ghana. The school is located at the outskirts of the town, geographically, in the Northern part of the town. The school has a student population of six hundred and offers the following programs: Science, General Arts, Visual Arts and Home Economics. The major research design adopted for this research was Action Research Design which made use of a Case Study at Siddiq Senior High School. Cohen and Manion (1994) defined action research as a small-scale intervention in the functioning of the real world and a close examination of the effects of such an intervention. This study was conducted with students’ population of 600 as at the time of this research. The accessible population of the study was made up of all the 35 second year students of the Science class who make up 5.83% of the school’s population. Out of the 35 students, 25 representing 71.43% of the class were boys whilst

the remaining 10 representing 28.57% were girls. The sampling technique used by the researcher is purposive sampling. As Johnson and Christensen (2000) pointed out, in purposive sampling, the researcher specifies the characteristics of a population of interest and then tries to locate individuals who have those characteristics. Prior to the intervention activities, the Researcher identified the problem when teaching the human digestive system in Form Two Science. To provide a way forward, the Researcher decided to employ a cooperative teaching strategy with the help of a well-prepared Teaching and Learning Materials to teach the concept, the human digestive system.

Data collection procedures

The main instrument used in the collection of data was Class Test. A class test was conducted to find out the magnitude of the perceived problem. The class test consisted of two parts. The first part was to assess the level of the students' knowledge in determining the parts of the human digestive system while the second part was to assess their level of knowledge in relating the parts of the digestive to their functions. Again, there were ten questions in each part. In all, there were twenty questions for the class test. Ten marks were allocated for each part, meaning each question attracted one mark, making the total marks allocated for the test twenty. The scores of the students were categorized into three; low scores (0-4), average scores (5-7) and high scores (8-10).

Validity of both the pre-test and post-test were ensured by structuring the questions in consonance with the demands of the Biology Syllabus. Also, the items were given to my mentor to examine and help correct any validity problem, be it content, construct, or face validity. The test items were also constructed to match the outcome being measured. The difficulty level of both the pre-test and the post-test were at the level of the students. Poorly constructed items were substituted with more appropriate ones after examination of the items by my mentor. The test items were based on the research question to ensure content validity of the instrument. Also, both pre-test and post-test items were scored using scoring rubric that was carefully and objectively prepared by me. This was to avert carry-over which could interfere with the soundness of the interpretation and use of the assessment results. To ensure reliability of the test items, both pre-test and post-test were re-administered to the same class two days after their administration and the scores were matched to ascertain whether they produced the same effect. This is called test-retest reliability.

Furthermore, before the class test was administered, the students were duly informed. It was administered with the help of my mentor who helped me ensure that the invigilation was done properly to ensure that none of the students cheated to obtain a reliable data. The duration for the class test was 30 minutes. The number of students present at the time of the administration of the test was 35. Finally, the data collected was analyzed using frequency tables.

The Post – intervention test was conducted after the intervention activities. This was meant to assess the effectiveness of intervention on the sub-topics under Human Digestive System. The post – test involved test that had the same content as the pre-intervention test administered. The results were also collated, and students’ marks were categorised based on low scores (0-4), average scores (5-7) and high scores (8-10). Descriptive statistics was then used to analyse the results.

Results

Pre intervention Data and Analysis

To diagnose the problem, a pre-intervention performance level of students on the parts and functions of the human digestive system, a test was conducted (See Appendix A). Results were presented in Table 1 and 2 as shown below.

Table 1: Scores obtained by Students in Pre – test (part one): Identification of Parts of the Human Digestive System

Scores Range	No. of Students	Percentages (%)
0-4	25	71.43
5-7	7	20
8-10	3	8.57
Total	35	100.00

Table 2: Scores obtained by Students in Pre – test (part two): Functions of parts of the Human Digestive System

Scores Range	No. of Students	Percentages (%)
0-4	28	80
5-7	4	11.43
8-10	3	8.57
Total	35	100.00

Table 1 indicates that 25 students representing 71.43% of the students in the class scored marks below average (pass mark of 5). This suggests that more than 50% of the students in the class could not properly answer questions relating to the parts of the human digestive system. Also, 7 students representing 20% of the students performed averagely whilst only 3 students representing 8.57% of the class performed above average and had scores within 8-10.

Again, for table 2, 28 students representing 80% of the students in the class scored marks below average (pass mark of 5). This also suggests that more than 50% of the students in the class could not properly answer questions relating to the functions of the parts of the human digestive system. Also, 4 students representing 11.4% of the students performed averagely whilst only 3 students representing 8.57% of the class performed above average and had scores within 8-10.

4.2 Post- intervention Data and Analysis

After the intervention, the researcher conducted another similar class test to find out how students responded to the intervention. Table 3 and 4 show the results obtained by students in the post intervention test.

Table 3: Scores obtained by Students in Post – test (part one): Identification of Parts of the Part of the Human Digestive System

Scores Range	No. of Students	Percentages (%)
0-4	2	5.71
5-7	12	34.29
8-10	21	60.00
Total	35	100

Table 4: Scores obtained by Students in pre – test (part two): Functions of Parts of the Human Digestive System

Scores Range	No. of Students	Percentages (%)
0-4	2	5.71
5-7	15	42.86
8-10	18	51.43
Total	35	100

Table 3 indicates that 2 students representing 5.71% of the class scored marks below average (pass mark of 5). This suggests that 5.71% of the students in the class could not properly answer questions relating to the parts of the human digestive system. Also, 12 students representing 34.29% of the students performed on average while an overwhelming 21 students representing 60% of the class performed above average and had scores within 8-10.

Table 4 indicates that 2 students representing 5.71% of the class scored marks below average (pass mark of 5). This suggests only 5.71% of the class could not properly answer questions relating to the parts of the human digestive system. Also, 15 students representing 42.86% of the students performed averagely whilst 18 students representing 51.43% of the class performed above average and had scores within 8-10.

Discussion of results

To address the research question, a pretest was designed to assess two aspects of human digestive system, namely, identifying the parts of the human digestive system and stating the functions of the human digestive system during the pre-intervention stage. From table one, 25 students representing 71.43% of the students in the class scored marks below average (pass mark of 5). This means more than half of the class could not correctly answer questions relating to the parts of the human digestive system which includes stating the parts of the human digestive system, stating the shapes of some organs of the human digestive system and distinguishing Gastrointestinal organs from the Accessory organs. Also, 7 students representing 20% of the students performed averagely. This means, the students scored slightly above the pass mark of five (7). This was not convincing enough. Again, only 3 students representing 8.57% of the class performed above average and had scores within 8-10. This means only a few students were able to score high marks. Again, table 2 showed that 28 students representing 80% of the sample population had below the pass mark of five meaning they could not state correct functions of the parts of human digestive system. Only 4 students representing 11.43% of the students performed

on average while only 3 students representing 8.57% of the class performed above average and had scores within 8-10. This revealed that the students really had difficulty in human digestive system. It was crystal clear from the discussions that the results obtained from the pretest were below standard, hence the adoption of the necessary intervention activities.

The students' data obtained from pre-test and post-test were compared. Just like the pre-test, the test was designed for students to state the parts of the human digestive system state the shapes of some organs of the human digestive system and distinguish Gastrointestinal organs from the Accessory organs. Table 3 indicates that 2 students representing 5.71% of the class scored marks below average (pass mark of 5). This suggests that 5.71% of the students in the class could not properly answer questions relating to the parts of the human digestive system.

Also, 12 students representing 34.43% of the students performed averagely while an overwhelming of 21 students representing 60% of the class performed above average and had scores within 8-10. Comparatively, there is a significant improvement with reference to the pre-test. This is because in the pretest 71.43% scored below average pass mark of 5 whilst in the posttest only 5.71% of the class scored below the pass mark of 5. Again, in the pretest 20% of the class scored the pass mark of 5 and above as against 34.29% in the post test. Moreso, in the pretest only 3 students representing 8.57% of the students scored above the average score as against 21 representing 60% of the class in the post test.

Table 4 indicates that 2 students representing 5.71% of the class scored marks below average (pass mark of 5). This suggests only 5.71% of the class could not properly answer questions relating to the parts of the human digestive system. Also, 15 students representing 42.86% of the students performed averagely whilst 18 students representing 51.43% of the class performed above average and had scores within 8-10. Just like the pre- test, the test was designed for students to relate the parts of the human digestive system to their functions. Comparatively, there is a significant improvement with reference to the pre-test. This is because in the pretest 80% of the class scored below average pass mark of 5 whilst in the posttest only 5.71% of the class scored below the pass mark of 5. Again, in the pretest 20% of the class scored the pass mark of 5 and above as against 42.86% in the post test. Moreso, in the pretest only 3 students representing 8.57% of the students scored above the average score as against 18 representing 51.43% of the class in the post test. In conclusion, the intervention activities did result in the enhancement of students understanding of the concept of the human digestive system.

The present study's overall findings corroborate with the study of Dei, Eminah, and Konadu (2025) which investigated the effect of cooperative instructional approach on the performance of Form One General Science students in chemical bonding in science. Their study adopted an action research design and utilized the purposive sampling technique to select an intact class of forty (40) students for the research. Data was gathered using tests and analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics. The findings of their study indicated that students exhibited a notable improvement in academic performance from the pre-intervention test (Mean=

6.18) to the post-intervention test (Mean=9.84). The t-test analysis revealed a statistically significant difference between the pre-intervention test mean score and the post-intervention test mean score ($p=0.037$; $p<0.05$). Also, their study revealed that students possess certain ideas about chemical bonding and face difficulties during lessons. However, the result of the teaching approach of the present study contradicts with that of Anthony and Konadu (2025), which concluded that teaching methods develop with experience, and the accumulation of expertise in the subject enhances the ability to transfer information to students. One teaching method alone is insufficient to ensure a learner's academic success. Children are distinct people possessing varied learning methods, capabilities, and personalities. What is effective for one child may not be effective for another.

Implications of the study

Research findings are very important; provide information for decision making. "Research can shed light on issues we did not even know existed and can raise questions we had not realized even needed asking". (Terry Freeman, 2011). Therefore, there is the need for research to be conducted in our schools to discover challenges that the students face as far as teaching and learning are concerned. First, this study will help students in S.H.S, two science students, to understand the concept of the human digestive system well. Secondly, it will help improve the performance of the students in WASSCE Biology paper. Thirdly, it will serve as a guide to Biology teachers. Again, it will also serve as a guide to practicing teachers for future comparative studies. Finally, it will help me to overcome similar challenges that may confront me during my professional career as a teacher.

Limitations

This study was restricted to only the chosen class, SHS two science at Siddiq Senior High School in Agona Nyarkrom. It could have been very appropriate and beneficial to include all the students in the school. However, this could not materialize due to inadequate resources and funds, and the time was limited.

Conclusion and recommendations

The purpose of this study was to improve students' understanding in human digestive system using Cooperative Teaching Approach in Siddiq Senior High School in Agona Nyarkrom in the Central Region of the Republic of Ghana. The intervention activities brought about improvement in students' understanding in identification of parts of the human digestive system and functions of the parts of human digestive system. The results of the pre-test showed that majority of the target group did not do well; none of them was able to score marks ranging from five to ten in both identifying the parts and also relating the parts to their functions of the human digestive system. This implies that the students had difficulty in human digestive system which needed attention. The post-test showed that majority of the students of the accessible group passed with

marks ranging between ten and twenty inclusive. One may find from the pre-test and the post-test that the accessible group performance improved after the intervention. This improvement was because of the intervention strategies that the students were taking through. By Mills (2003), action research is conducted with the goals of gaining insight, developing reflective practice and improving students' outcome. As I analyzed the data collected during this research, I was able to achieve all the two goals outlined. I gained considerable insight concerning my students' understanding in human digestive system and the use of Cooperative Teaching Approach as Biology Teacher. I refined my reflective practice habits related to improving my instruction, and my students showed a great deal of growth in their understanding of human digestives. Based on the findings of the study and the conclusion drawn, the researcher recommends the following;

- ❖ Biology teachers should involve students in cooperative small group instruction to help students learn better.
- ❖ That student-centered approach to teaching should be adopted in teaching human digestive system.
- ❖ It is very necessary for science teachers to take their time in teaching abstract topics like the digestive system in humans. This is because this concept runs through most fields of biological sciences. The teacher therefore must ensure that the concept is well understood by students.

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